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PROBLEMS OF THE FINANCIAL MECHANISM INFLUENCE FOR STABLE AND INERTIAL DEVELOPMENT OF ENTERPRISES

Zaynalov Jakhongir Rasulovich

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Email: ZaynalovJakhongir@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-5141-544X

Alieva Susanna

Associate Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Email: alievasusanna@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-3337-1743

Abstract: The article covers the financial mechanism for ensuring the inertia of enterprises. The essential aspects of the financial mechanism for regulating the inertia of stable development of enterprises are considered, the author's approaches to disclosing the meaning of "inertia", the stability of development of enterprises are given, in addition, a number of proposals and recommendations are given for improving the mechanism of influence on the inertia of development of enterprises.

Key words: cost, efficiency, financial mechanism, innovation orientation, investment-oriented development of the enterprise, elements of connections, inertia, financial mechanism for managing the inertia of enterprises, situational regulation, inertial properties of enterprises, reliability.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada korxonalarning inertsiyasini ta'minlashning moliyaviy mexanizmi yoritilgan. Korxonalarning barqaror rivojlanishi inertsiyasini tartibga solishning moliyaviy mexanizmining muhim jihatlari ko'rib chiqiladi, "inertsiya" ma'nosini ochib berish bo'yicha muallifning yondashuvlari, korxonalarning rivojlanish barqarorligi, bundan tashqari, korxonalarning rivojlanish inertsiyasiga ta'sir qilish mexanizmini takomillashtirish bo'yicha bir qator takliflar va tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xarajat, samaradorlik, moliyaviy mexanizm, innovatsiyaga yo'naltirilganlik, korxonaning investitsiyaga yo'naltirilgan rivojlanishi, bog'lanish elementlari, inertsiya, korxonalar inertsiyasini boshqarishning moliyaviy mexanizmi, vaziyatni tartibga solish, korxonalarning inertial xususiyatlari, ishonchlilik.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается финансовый механизм обеспечения инерционности предприятий. Рассмотрены существенные аспекты финансового механизма регулирования инерционности устойчивого развития предприятий, приведены авторские подходы к раскрытию содержания понятий «инерционность», устойчивость развития предприятий, кроме того, дан ряд предложений и рекомендаций по совершенствованию механизма воздействия на инерционность развития предприятий.

Ключевые слова: стоимость, эффективность, финансовый механизм, инновационная направленность, инвестиционно-ориентированное развитие предприятия, элементы связей, инерционность, финансовый механизм управления инерционностью предприятий, ситуационное регулирование, инерционные свойства предприятий, надежность.

INTRODUCTION

The issue of sustainable development will not be revealed if we do not talk about the improvement of the main financial indicators of the activities of a particular enterprise.

It is known that in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, enterprises are influenced by factors of both internal and external environment. The former, in our opinion, include factors that depend on the financial and production activities of enterprises. The latter are factors that do not depend not only on production activities,

but also on factors that affect the level of use of production and financial resources of enterprises. As these factors influencing the formation of stability of enterprise development, we can highlight pricing, management, production, financial, business strategies.

In general, the concept of ensuring stable development of an enterprise requires a continuous process of improving the above strategies, as well as addressing the insufficiently studied properties of the production system, which include the property of enterprise inertia. It is from this position that one can interpret the main provisions in the Concept of the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Stable Development for 2022-2026, where the emphasis is on the stability of macroeconomic development, in which the enterprise is of paramount importance. It is known that inertia is inherent in any economic system, but in the theory and practice of the strategy of stable development of enterprises, there are still no methods for measuring the indicator of enterprise inertia that would allow solving a number of problems that reduce the effectiveness of existing mechanisms for the stable development of enterprises. The course of the approach taken to the study of inertia and its impact on the conditions for the stable development of enterprises with an innovative focus allows us to obtain and apply new knowledge to develop correct methods and models, as well as improve the mechanism for the stable development of an enterprise. In connection with the need to take into account the internal and external environment of the enterprise, it will also be possible to determine the higher relevance and significance of the task of forming such a problem-oriented financial mechanism for the stable development of the enterprise, in which, through regulation of its inertial properties, an increase in efficiency and competitiveness is ensured, as the most important characteristics for the survival and development of the enterprise.

In economic literature, the term «financial mechanism of inertia management» has not yet been encountered. Although the term itself is often encountered in both economic and technical sciences. Therefore, studying the financial mechanism within the framework of inertia is important.

In our opinion, the problem-oriented mechanism of stable development of the enterprise is a mechanism executed by inertia, capable of ensuring stable development of enterprises by solving one or several homogeneous problems that impede development, designed to complement the existing financial mechanism of enterprise management or its stable development and increasing its efficiency. The essence of the developed problem-oriented financial mechanism of managing the stable development of the enterprise is associated with the financial management of the enterprise inertia, which should ensure the acceleration of the implementation of innovations and an increase in the efficiency of the enterprise, including profit. Such a specific financial mechanism is distinguished by its own set of elements and connections, target, controlled, providing subsystems and methods, which are designed to implement financial management of the enterprise inertia and form control actions that improve the conditions for the stable development of the enterprise, increase its quality indicators and accelerate adaptation and innovative transformations.

The financial mechanism we are noting affects the parameters of the enterprise and thereby reduces its inertia, resistance to change. This is where the essence of general financial management of inertia is manifested. Additionally, the financial mechanism can provide for situational financial management of inertia, which determines the development of sets of financial mechanisms of influence corresponding to typical situations of adaptation or innovative transformations, with the purpose of accelerating them and increasing the efficiency of the enterprise. Thus, for example, we presented the information support system of the financial mechanism for managing the inertia of the enterprise as a set of two subsystems for managing the inertia of the enterprise:

Financial mechanism of general management of enterprise inertia, including such methods and processes of financial management as: stimulation of innovative behavior, personnel activity; creation of conditions for effective functioning of enterprises; training and advanced training of entrepreneurs, performers; innovation planning and change management; explanation to employees of the essence of business plans and prospects for enterprise development; correction of the organizational culture of the enterprise; rationalization of business processes and updating of standards; creation of flexible production; formation of a fund of resources necessary for implementation of changes, management of inertia and stable development of the enterprise; monitoring and analysis of factors used in regulation of stable development and inertia of the enterprise, and indicators that track the results of financial stability of development and inertia of the enterprise.

A financial mechanism for situational regulation of enterprise inertia, including such methods and processes of regulation as: classification and description of typical (standard) management situations; development of situational plans and preventive measures; preparatory and preventive measures that improve the inertial properties of an enterprise; modeling, analysis and forecasting of change periods, possible results (economic benefits), risks, costs, missed opportunities; identification of transformation centers.

The proposed financial mechanism takes into account the influence of inertia on the inertial properties of the enterprise and its individual elements, including technical, technological, methodological (organizational

and managerial), financial and economic, information and communication, and innovative and entrepreneurial.

It is possible to note the dependence of the stable development of the enterprise on its inertia, which is manifested through resistance to innovative changes. The need to manage inertia determines the problem-oriented orientation of the financial mechanism that ensures the stable development of the enterprise and is intended to complement its management system.

Having analyzed the essence of the financial mechanism, it was revealed that the concepts of «stability», «stable development» and «inertia of the economic system» are different and incompatible, since inertia is an integral property of financial and economic activity, and «stability» is its possible state. Its stable development, i.e. the economic system, as well as any enterprise, is associated with the growth of the volume of sales of its own products, innovations and the cyclical nature of the development process. Innovations qualitatively change the activity of any enterprise, but encounter resistance from the system, this is where the essence of such a complex economic phenomenon as inertia is manifested. Inertia, of course, causes a delay in the reaction of the financial mechanism to changes and innovations in the external and internal environment. By managing inertia, we can achieve a decrease in resistance to innovations, accelerate the process of their implementation and commercial use, and therefore improve the conditions for the stable development of enterprises.

RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

A systemic analysis of existing problem-oriented financial mechanisms, including mechanisms for stable development, shows that they do not provide for the management of enterprise inertia. The development of the latter, associated with innovations and their commercial use, runs into their inertia as a problem, which is largely determined by consumer resistance. This problem, as a consequence, leads to a decrease in financial efficiency, primarily labor productivity, delays in development and a decrease in enterprise profits.

In management practice, many tools are used within the framework of mechanisms. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze general (complex) financial management mechanisms, including stable development of the enterprise. Our analysis showed that most authors (more than 98%) highlight individual aspects and problems of the financial management mechanism and build problem-oriented financial mechanisms, which include: innovation-oriented; information-oriented; investment-oriented; integration-oriented; aimed at identifying and using financial resources and reserves of production (growth, development), increasing efficiency, reliability, competitiveness; adaptive; anti-crisis; coordination and harmonization of supply, production and sales processes; risk management.

Thus, problem-oriented financial mechanisms of inertia management can be attributed to a separate class. It is substantiated that the resistance of the financial mechanism to changes allows us to identify indicators characterizing inertia, measure them and manage inertia, supplementing the known financial mechanisms with problem-oriented management of inertia, creating conditions for stable development, preventive management of the properties of the financial system, counteracting negative environmental impacts and resistance to adaptive and innovative changes. The financial mechanism being developed can supplement the existing financial mechanisms and systems of financial management of enterprise development at enterprises in order to increase their efficiency and improve the dynamics of innovative development.

CONCLUSION

An analysis of the theoretical foundations of the problem-oriented financial mechanism for the stable development of an enterprise, the essence, features, conditions, factors and methods that determine its formation, will allow us to select a set of methods and organizational forms, as well as develop a basic diagram of the problem-oriented financial mechanism.

In practice, the methods and means of analysis and financial management of enterprise inertia can be divided into 15 groups (technical; technological; objects of labor; logistic; labor; innovation-entrepreneurial; financial-investment; economic; systemic; information-communication; methodological; organizational; legal; cultural; socio-psychological) and 2 classes (methods and means of resisting the destruction of the enterprise's economic system; methods and means of accelerating development and increasing the stability of enterprise development).

A special role in the financial mechanism being developed can be given to methods of influencing the inertia of the enterprise by means of personnel management.

To implement a problem-oriented financial mechanism, it is also recommended to develop a comprehensive program for improving financial management of the stable development of the enterprise.

References:

1. Nedzinskas, Š., Pundzienė, A., Buožiūtė-Rafanavičienė, S., & Pilkienė, M. (2013). The impact of dynamic capabilities on SME performance in a volatile environment as moderated by organizational inertia. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 8(4), 376-396.
2. Lin, J. Y., Sun, X., & Jiang, Y. (2009). Toward a theory of optimal financial structure. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (5038).
3. Jui-Chan, H., Lu, C., Hao-Ming, W., Ching-Tang, H., & Hui-Wen, W. (2020). The study of organizational inertia, business model innovation and organizational performance in Taiwan financial institutions: Organizational learning perspective. *Revista Argentina de Clínica Psicológica*, 29(5), 104.
4. Li, S. X., & Rowley, T. J. (2002). Inertia and evaluation mechanisms in interorganizational partner selection: Syndicate formation among US investment banks. *Academy of Management journal*, 45(6), 1104-1119.
5. Liao, S. H., Fei, W. C., & Liu, C. T. (2008). Relationships between knowledge inertia, organizational learning and organization innovation. *Technovation*, 28(4), 183-195.
6. Wan, Y., Sheng, N., Wei, X., & Su, H. (2023). Study on the spatial spillover effect and path mechanism of green finance development on China's energy structure transformation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 415, 137820.

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